

STUDIES IN CATALYTIC DEHYDROGENATION. PART II

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1:2:3:4-Tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-(3'-methylcyclopentane) and its 7-methyl derivative have been synthesised and their catalytic dehydrogenation with Pt-C studied. The former gave 2-methylphenanthrene as the only dehydrogenation product, whereas the latter gave 3:6-dimethylphenanthrene along with a small amount of anthracene derivatives.

We synthesised the two tetrahydronaphthalene-spiro-cyclopentanes, namely 1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-(3'-methylcyclopentane) (IV, R=H; R'=Me) and its 7-methyl derivative (IV, R=R'=Me), each having a methyl group in the spiro-cyclopentane ring, in order to study the behaviour of the methyl group during catalytic dehydrogenation of these spiro-compounds. It was found that the spiro-hydrocarbon (IV, R=H; R'=Me) underwent simultaneous dehydrogenation and ring transformation when heated with Pt-C catalyst at 300°-320° with the formation of 2-methylphenanthrene as the only product. The formation of any anthracene derivative could not be detected. When the spiro-hydrocarbon (IV, R=R'=Me), however, was dehydrogenated under a similar condition, it was found that though the main dehydrogenation product was 3:6-dimethylphenanthrene, a small amount of a high melting hydrocarbon could be isolated which seemed to be a mixture of 2:6-dimethyl- and 2:7-dimethylanthracenes. So it was found that in both the cases though ring transformation took place during catalytic dehydrogenation, the methyl group present in the spiro-cyclopentane ring was not expelled.

The two spiro-hydrocarbons were synthesised by an extension of the method followed in Part I of this series (*this Journal*, 1952, 29, 331). The anhydride of 3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid was condensed with benzene in presence of aluminium chloride affording $\alpha\alpha$ -(3'-methylcyclopentane)- β -benzoylpropionic acid (I, R=H; R'=Me) and this on Clemmensen reduction gave $\alpha\alpha$ -(3'-methylcyclopentane)- γ -phenylbutyric acid (II, R=H; R'=Me) (Desai and Wali, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1937, 6A, 141). The latter on cyclisation with 85% sulphuric acid gave 1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-(3'-methylcyclopentane) (III, R=H; R'=Me). The spiro-ketone on Clemmensen reduction gave 1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-(3'-methylcyclopentane) (IV, R=H; R'=Me).

In a similar manner 7-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-(3'-methylcyclopentane) (IV, R=R'=Me) was synthesised starting from toluene

and anhydride of 3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid. Structures of the keto-acids (I, R=H; R'=Me) and (I, R=R'-Me) had been proved by Desai and Wali (*loc. cit.*) as containing a CH₂.CO grouping.

EXPERIMENTAL

$\alpha\alpha$ -(3'-Methylcyclopentane)- β -benzoylpropionic acid (I, R=H; R'=Me) and $\alpha\alpha$ -(3'-methylcyclopentane)- γ -phenylbutyric acid (II, R=H; R'=Me) were prepared according to Desai and Wali (*loc. cit.*). This butyric acid was best purified by distillation under reduced pressure and crystallisation from petroleum ether.

1-Keto-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2 : 2-spiro-(3'-methylcyclopentane) (III, R=H; R'=Me).—The butyric acid (II, R=H; R'=Me) (7g.) was heated with 85% sulphuric acid (28 c.c.) at 100° for 1½ hours with stirring. The product was poured on ice, extracted with ether and the ether extract was washed with dilute ammonia, dried and distilled. It is a viscous oil with a characteristic odour, b. p. 137°–140°/5mm., yield 5 g. (Found : C, 83.9; H, 8.5. C₁₅H₁₈O requires C, 84.1; H, 8.4 per cent).

1 : 2 : 3 : 4-Tetrahydronaphthalene-2 : 2-spiro-(3'-methylcyclopentane) (IV, R=H; R'=Me).—The spiro-ketone (III, R=H; R'=Me) (5 g.) was boiled with amalgamated zinc (20 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c. c.) for 24 hours. The product was a colorless liquid, b. p. 122°–125°/5 mm., yield 3 g. (Found : C, 89.7; H, 10.2. C₁₅H₂₀ requires C, 90.0; H, 10.0 per cent).

Dehydrogenation of the Spiro-hydrocarbon (IV, R=H; R'=Me).—The spiro-hydrocarbon (3 g.) was heated with Pt-C catalyst (0.3g.) in a metal-bath at 300°–310° for 6 hours and at 310°–320° for 6 hours when no further hydrogen was evolved. The product was thoroughly extracted with ether and benzene and distilled over sodium under reduced pressure. The distillate readily solidified on cooling, yield 1 g. The distillate was converted into picrate which crystallised from rectified spirit in orange needles, m. p. 119°–20°. The hydrocarbon was regenerated from the picrate and crystallised from methyl alcohol in plates, m. p. 53–54°. The mixed m. p. of the hydrocarbon with a sample of 2-methylphenanthrene and that of its picrate with the picrate of 2-methylphenanthrene remained unaltered.

$\alpha\alpha$ -(3'-Methylcyclopentane)- β -(*p*-toluyl)propionic acid (I, R=R'-Me) was prepared as described by Desai and Wali (*loc. cit.*). Its semicarbazone crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 175–76° (decomp.). (Found : C, 64.1; H, 7.5. C₁₇H₂₃O₃N₃ requires C, 64.35; H, 7.25 per cent). This keto-acid gave $\alpha\alpha$ -(3'-methylcyclopentane)- γ -(*p*-tolyl)butyric acid (Desai and Wali, *loc. cit.*) on Clemmensen reduction.

1-Keto-7-methyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2 : 2-spiro-(3'-methylcyclopentane) (III, R=R'-Me).—The butyric acid (III, R=R'-Me) (10 g.) was heated

on a steam-bath with 85% sulphuric acid (40 c. c.) for 1½ hours with stirring. The product was purified just as in the case of the ketone (III, R=H; R'=Me). It is a colorless liquid with a characteristic odour, b. p. 160–161°/5 mm., yield 6 g. (Found : C, 83.8; H, 9.0. C₁₆H₂₀O requires C, 84.2; H, 8.8 per cent).

The *oxime* of this spiro-ketone was obtained by heating it with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in pyridine solution for 6 hours. It crystallised from methyl alcohol in needles, m. p. 112–113°. (Found : C, 78.7; H, 8.7. C₁₆H₂₁ON requires C, 79.0; H, 8.6 per cent).

7-Methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-(3'-methylcyclopentane) (IV, R=R'=Me).—The spiro-ketone (III, R=R'=Me) (5.5 g) was heated with amalgamated zinc (22 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (22 c. c.) for 24 hours. The product was extracted with ether, washed, dried and distilled. It is a liquid, b. p. 135°–137°/5 mm., yield 4 g. (Found : C, 89.4; H, 10.4. C₁₆H₂₂ requires C, 89.7; H, 10.3 per cent).

Dehydrogenation of the Spiro-hydrocarbon (IV, R=R'=Me).—The spiro-hydrocarbon (3 g.) was heated with Pt-C catalyst (0.3 g.) in a metal-bath at 300°–310. for 6 hours and at 310°–320° for 6 hours when dehydrogenation was complete. The product was thoroughly extracted with ether and benzene and was distilled over sodium under reduced pressure. The first fraction collected at 170°–175°/5 mm. as a solid with a greenish fluorescence, yield 2 g. The second fraction was collected at a much higher temperature as a yellowish solid, yield 0.5 g.

(a). The first fraction was converted into picrate in alcoholic solution, and crystallised thrice from rectified spirit and the hydrocarbon was regenerated from the picrate. The hydrocarbon crystallised from rectified spirit as thin flakes, m. p. 140°. (Found : C, 93.1; H, 6.9. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₄ : C, 93.2; H, 6.8 per cent). The picrate prepared from the regenerated hydrocarbon was crystallised from rectified spirit in orange needles, m. p. 174°. Haworth records the m. p. of 3:6-dimethylphenanthrene as 140–41° and that of its picrate as 172–73° (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 460).

(b). The second fraction was twice crystallised from methyl alcohol and obtained in shining flakes with bluish fluorescence, m. p. 225°. The high m. p. of the product indicated that probably it was a mixture of 2:6-dimethyl- and 2:7-dimethylanthracene (cf. Morgan, *ibid.*, 1929, 2203). With the small amount of the material at our disposal, separation of the isomeric anthracenes could not be effected.

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